

Best practices and guidelines for metadata mapping, linking, and integration

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Version: 1.0

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15780729

2025-06-30

Project KGI4NFDI - Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for the German National Research Data Infrastructure

Work Package 3 Interoperability Strategy

Deliverable D3.1 Strategy for metadata mapping, linking, and integration

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the [German Research Foundation](#) under the grant number 521453681.

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Overview

Interoperability is crucial in the context of Knowledge Graphs (KG) because it enables seamless data integration, exchange, and reuse across different systems, domains, and organizations. By adhering to established standards, such as those for representation (RDF, Labelled Property Graphs, etc.), or querying ([SPARQL](#), [Graph Query Language](#), etc.), interoperable KGs ensure that diverse datasets can be linked and understood in a unified way, reducing data silos, and enhancing discoverability. This is especially important for applications in artificial intelligence, semantic search, and decision-making, where the ability to connect and reason over heterogeneous data sources leads to more accurate insights and better-informed decisions.

Disclaimer: The best practices and examples described in this document focus on RDF graph representation based on design decisions for the KGI Registry. It is important to mention that other representations like LPG face similar challenges.

Existing interoperability frameworks

In the context of KG interoperability, we identified several relevant (framework) initiatives, both national and international in scope (see Table 1). Some of these initiatives have a broader view on interoperability and go beyond KGs. EIF, among other objectives, strives for reuse and sharing of information and data for European public services, whereas GORC targets research artifacts. Moreover, CDIF and FAIRsFAIR support the adoption of FAIR principles for more multidisciplinary research (cross domain and cross infrastructure access and reuse), and throughout the research life cycle, correspondingly. In a similar vein, SIMPL provides interoperability at the software solution level by enabling data exchange across different data space implementations, whereas the EDM initiative focuses on the metadata interoperability for the cultural heritage domain. In KGI4NFDI we consider the requirements from such different scopes that are related to or overlap with the KG context.

Name	Description	URL
EOSC Interoperability Framework	Brings together interoperability practices for both generic research infrastructure and specific domains.	https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/EIF.pdf
RDA Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF)	Supports the (data) exchange between initiatives that collect and manage scholarly content.	https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg/activity/
The European Interoperability Framework (EIF)	Consisting of principles, interoperability layers, and a conceptual model, it targets public digital services.	https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/eif_en/
Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)	Provides generic recommendations towards FAIR data.	https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/
Global Open Research Commons (GORC)	Works towards enabling an environment where research data and services can be shared.	https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/global-open-research-commons-ig/
SIMPL	Aims at interoperability/federation between data spaces.	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/simpl

Europeana Data Model (EDM)	Allows the collection, connection and enrichment of cultural heritage metadata.	https://pro.europeana.eu/page/meta-data
Cross-Domain Interoperability of Heterogeneous Research Data (GO-FAIR Inter)	Focuses on practices that support research data interoperability - methods, tools and guidelines - across domains (inactive).	https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/go-inter/
FAIRsFAIR	Provides practices for adopting FAIR principles across the research life cycle.	https://www.fairsfair.eu/

Table 1. Overview on interoperability frameworks from (inter)national initiatives

An important aspect we had into view was considering the alignment with relevant international bodies, such as those from the EU or the Research Data Alliance. For the following sections, we relied mostly on the EOSC Interoperability Framework and SKG-IF initiatives: the former covers a broad range of interoperability issues, whereas the latter focuses on scientific data and information.

Interoperability dimensions

Existing frameworks have already proved as a great starting point for the specification of interoperability issues for KGs. After an initial investigation of these frameworks, we identified several applicable interoperability dimensions in the context of KGI4NFDI (Table 2). We wanted to note that we make a distinction between interoperability challenges that occur during the **generation** and those during **access/(re)usage** of a KG, that is, the NFDI consortia adopting KGs in their projects are either in the process of generating/creating one, or they already have one that the rest of the NFDI community can access.

KG adoption phase	Dimension	Description
KG Generation	Graph representation	The representation model of the KG. <u>Examples:</u> RDF, Labeled Property Graph, etc.
	Metadata schemas, ontologies	The principle(s) that organize the metadata <u>Examples:</u> schema.org , NFDIcore , DCAT , Dublin Core , etc.
	Terminologies	Domain-specific terminologies, controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri, etc. <u>Examples:</u> STW , TheSoz , VIAF , GND , etc.
	Persistent Identifiers (PID)	The schema to use for the persistent identification of the resources. <u>Examples:</u> URIs, DOIs, Handles, URNs, etc.
KG Access	Application Programming Interfaces (API)	The API to be used for accessing and exchanging with a KG. <u>Examples:</u> SPARQL, REST API, JSON API, OAI-PMH API, ...

	User Interfaces (UI)	Exploration and visualization of a KG <u>Examples:</u> Gephi , Neo4j Bloom , etc.
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Table 2. Interoperability dimensions in KGI4NFDI

For the KG generation case, we consider the following aspects:

- **Graph representation:** In addition to the conceptual, added values, and use cases addressed, a KG generation project ultimately needs a materialization phase, during which the KG gets created and populated with the relevant resources. Thus, the way to represent the data becomes important. With the proliferation of KG generation come several representation models, most notable of which are W3C's Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Labeled Property Graph (LPG). Both models hold different characteristics and facilitate different use cases. Although we have not documented other cases across NFDI consortia, we see other models being adopted as well.
- **Metadata schemas, ontologies** KGs bring a certain uniformity to the resources they are populated with. In this way, a common, overarching (semantic) layer to describe all the resources is adopted and adhered to. This layer can be of different characteristics, such based on a (combination of) metadata schema, ontology, or other structures that support the description of the resources, their attributes, and the relationships between them.
- **Terminologies** Every community or domain usually has their set of values to describe resources according to a given semantic layer. For example, for the same metadata schema, a community might differ from another community in terms of the allowed values for the same element to that metadata schema. During KG generation, it is important to support the use of relevant terminologies for the consortia.
- **Persistent Identifiers** The same benefits that we get from assigning PIDs to our publications and datasets, also apply for KG generation: a KG resource with an assigned PID - mandatory in some graph representations - supports a persistent identification and, thus, findability.

For the KG access phase, we consider the following dimensions:

- **Application Programming Interfaces (API)** There are different ways of accessing a KG. While a SPARQL endpoint is the most native access for RDF graphs, other established APIs allow for accessing the data from a graph as well. The decision of which interface to choose for accessing a graph depends often on how the retrieved data is wished to be consumed or further processed. The decision of which interface to provide access to a graph as a provider depends often on performance aspects and compatibility with interfaces of the designated stakeholders.
- **User Interfaces (UI)** The content of a KG is semantically rich, but may also be quite complex, particularly for users who are not familiar with KGs or graph-based data structures. To facilitate consumption of KG data, various tools exist which provide user-friendly interfaces, e.g. visualization tools.

It is worth mentioning that, as the practices across NFDI consortia change, we will try to reflect them and adjust the dimensions accordingly.

Interoperability in the context of metadata mapping, linking and integration

We define the three terms of metadata mapping, metadata linking, and metadata integration as follows:

- **Metadata Mapping** refers to aligning metadata schemas or structures from different sources to ensure consistency and interoperability. It involves creating correspondences between different vocabularies or ontologies, enabling data to be interpreted in a unified way.

- **Metadata Linking** involves establishing explicit relationships between metadata entities across different datasets, often using unique identifiers (e.g., URIs). This allows for seamless navigation and retrieval of interconnected information within a knowledge graph.
- **Metadata Integration** is the process of merging metadata from multiple sources into a cohesive KG, resolving conflicts, harmonizing formats, and ensuring semantic consistency. It enables comprehensive and enriched data representation for advanced querying like federated queries and analysis.

Mapping, linking, and integration of metadata and metadata schemas is key for the interoperability between KGs because it can facilitate the alignment, understanding, and utilization of resources across different systems of diverse datasets. By bringing representation models and resource description together, as already mentioned, standardized frameworks and protocols, such as RDF, OWL, or schema.org, enable this, facilitating meaningful connections between disparate data sources. This enhances data discoverability, consistency, and usability while reducing redundancy and fragmentation. Eventually, data exchange, analytics, and retrieval in single KGs or across KGs by federated queries is facilitated.

Federated queries

A concrete example of interoperability is the idea of querying more than one KG in one query, which is known as query federation, or simply federation. Such federated queries have parts that run on one KG and pass on intermediate results to one or more additional KGs, from which final results can be determined. The main use case for this is data fusion from different KGs, where one acts to filter, enrich or otherwise process the results from the other KGs. For federation to work, the KGs combined in the query need to have some content overlap, and the content needs to be modeled on each end such that a correspondence to the representation on the other end can be established. In Tables 4 and 5, we provide examples regarding the different representations of DOIs in a KG. Legal interoperability like license compatibility, as well as policy issues like allowlists for queries to and from other KGs are additional dimensions of to be considered for federated queries.

The current standard for SPARQL query federation was defined a decade ago¹, and an update is underway². As is the case with SPARQL itself, different vendors of KG engines comply with the federation standard in different ways. The use of several different KG engines within NFDI contexts complicates the picture for federation.

¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-federated-query/>

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql12-federated-query/>

Best practices

Before we move on with the best practices, we would like to point out their need and/or applicability for the NFDI community. Namely, based on the survey we conducted (Limani, 2025) as part of the project, we wanted to know the need or plans to connect the data of an organization or NFDI consortium with other such entities. Around 30% of the participants that answered this question stated that they aim to achieve this. This informs us that, ultimately, interoperability is going to play a role in such a project, thus, best practices related to it are suitable to support such efforts.

In this section, we provide several recommendations on (meta)data descriptions of KGs. Specifically, we provide recommendations of metadata schemas for describing specific scientific artifacts, their selection considerations, the usage of an NFDI-specific ontology, as well as recommendations for describing the (meta)data in a consistent way, including the use of terminologies.

Recommended metadata schemas for scientific artifacts

In Table 3, we provide an overview of recommended metadata schemas that can be used for describing specific scientific artifacts. These recommendations are based on metadata schemas used by KGs within the NFDI.

Scientific artifact	Name	Description	Example KGs
Creative works, Publications, Books, Datasets, Software, Persons, Organizations, Medical entities, ...	schema.org	Generic model for representing any web resource, provides classes and properties for a representation of various scientific artifacts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SoftwareKG • GESIS KG • Linked Stage Graph
NFDI consortia, including Research Data Infrastructures, Services, Projects, Data portals, Individuals, Organizations	NFDIcore	NFDIcore ontology provides classes and properties for metadata of resources in NFDI consortia. It promotes interoperability across resources in NFDI consortia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KGI4NFDI Registry • NFDI4Culture • Matwerk
Datasets, Data services, Data catalogs	DCAT	Designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogs published on the Web.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NFDI4Earth
Datasets, Publications, Webpages	Dublin Core Metadata Terms	Describing web resources of any type.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The official portal for European data
Survey data and all components of its lifecycle, including Datasets, Variables, Questionnaires, Questions, Survey instruments.	DDI	Describing social science data, data covering human activity, and other data based on observational methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GESIS KG
Terminologies, Controlled vocabularies, Taxonomies, Classifications	SKOS	Designed for representation of thesauri, classification schemes, taxonomies, subject-heading systems, or any other type of structured controlled	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph • NFDI4Earth

		vocabulary.	
Provenance information	Prov-O	Provides a set of classes, properties, and restrictions that can be used to represent and interchange provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SoMeSci • The official portal for European data
Social networks, Persons, Organizations	foaf	FOAF is a project devoted to linking people and information using the Web	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The official portal for European data • TweetsCov19
Sentences, Contexts, Phrases	NIF-Core	Provides classes and properties to describe the relations between substrings, text, documents by assigning URIs to strings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SoMeSci • ClaimsKG
Presentations, Data Reports, Databases, Conferences, Journal articles	fabio	Describing entities that are published or potentially publishable and are referred to by bibliographic references.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NFDI4Culture
Software applications, Software source code	CodeMeta	Metadata schema for science software and code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dagstuhl DROPS

Table 3. Overview on cross-disciplinary metadata schema/ontologies for scientific artifacts

Considerations on selecting metadata schemas and interoperability

When selecting metadata schemas for creating a KG with scientific artifacts, it is essential to consider compatibility, standardization, and domain relevance. Using well-established schemas like [Dublin Core](#), [schema.org](#), or domain-specific ontologies such as [OBO Foundry](#) ensures interoperability and alignment with existing scientific data infrastructures. Since KGs often integrate multiple schemas, ensuring compatibility through established mappings and links between metadata standards is crucial for seamless data integration. Mapping classes and properties across schemas helps maintain semantic consistency, enabling effective knowledge representation, retrieval, and reuse within the broader scientific ecosystem.

A comprehensive overview on metadata standards can be found in the [RDA Metadata Standards Catalog](#). Additionally, [FAIRsharing](#) offers a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies. [Linked Open Vocabularies \(LOV\)](#) provides search functionality over 874 vocabularies to find suitable vocabularies for representing data.

NFDIcore ontology

The [NFDIcore Ontology](#) is a standardized ontology designed to support interoperability and semantic integration across research data infrastructures, particularly within Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) initiative. It provides a core set of concepts and relationships for describing resources, services, and information within NFDI consortia which facilitates the integration and exchange of data across different disciplines and domains. For

example, in the KGI4NFDI registry, classes and properties from NFDIcore will be used to describe basic metadata about each KG like name, URL of the landing page, involved NFDI consortia, etc.

Consistent description of content

Consistently describing content in a KG is crucial for interoperability. Standardized metadata enables systems to understand and process information uniformly, reducing ambiguity and improving searchability, automation, and collaboration. Without consistency, data silos emerge, making it difficult to connect, share, and leverage knowledge effectively.

In a KG, metadata from instances can be described in different ways: as text, as numerical content (e.g. dates or numbers), URIs (leading to another resource within the same KG or within another, external one), or URLs (leading to a location on the web). In the RDF world, the type of the content can be decoded by attaching a `xsd:datatype` to an object which defines whether the content is a literal (i.e. text), an URI, or any kind of numerical content, e.g. years, date, integer values, etc.

For textual content, interoperability can be further increased if described in a consistent way, e.g. by applying rules for description including case-sensitivity, order, or patterns. As an example, one could agree that person names within a KG should always follow the pattern `[Lastname, Firstname]`. To increase semantic interpretation (whether by humans or machines), language tags can be used to determine the language the literal is encoded in. Moreover, concepts from terminologies can also help to describe content in a consistent way (see next section on the use of terminologies).

To illustrate the importance of describing content in a consistent way, we provide an example of the different ways a DOI may occur within a KG resource in Table 4. DOI values can be represented as follows:

Strings	which contain	the full URL	<code>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14844417</code>
		only some part	<code>10.5281/zenodo.14844417</code>
	whose capitalization is	not normalized	<code>10.5281/Zenodo.14844417</code>
		normalized, e.g., upper case or lower case	<code>10.5281/ZENODO.14844417</code>
URLs (that may be hyperlinked or not)	whose protocol prefix is	defined, e.g., http or https	<code>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14844417</code>
		not defined, or handled separately	<code>doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14844417</code>
	whose domain name	starts with doi.org	<code>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14844417</code>
		includes the (old) subdomain dx	<code>https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14844417</code>
	whose identifier part	is normalized or not	<code>https://doi.org/10.5281/zEnodo.14844417</code>

Table 4. Different representations of a DOI

Moreover, DOI relationships can be represented in various ways as well as shown in Table 5.

Digital Object Identifier
DOI
doi
digital_object_id
hasDOI
http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C71462
https://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C71462
http://id.loc.gov/authorities/subjects/sh99010374
https://www.ebi.ac.uk/miriam/main/datatypes/MIR:00000019
MIR:00000019
https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Property:P356
wikidata:P356
P356
디지털 객체 식별자
...

Table 5. Different relationships for pointing to a DOI

For the official DOI URI scheme specification, see <https://doi.org/10.1000/292>.

Use of terminologies

Knowledge graphs (KG) and terminologies are closely related, as both are used to structure and represent knowledge within a certain scope. Terminologies offer standardized vocabularies, comprising concepts, definitions, and relationships, which form the basis for constructing KGs. These KGs, in turn, organize terminologies into semantic layers interconnecting networks of data / knowledge, and thereby enabling semantic reasoning and data integration, e.g, by using standardized terms like concepts of a domain-specific thesaurus ambiguity within and across KGs can be reduced. By leveraging terminologies, KGs ensure consistency and interoperability across various applications, such as AI-assisted tools, information search, and data analytics.

Mapping and linking also play a role in the context of terminologies. The [Terminology Services 4 NFDI \(TS4NFDI\)](#) is a cross-domain service for the provision, curation, development, harmonization, and mapping of terminologies. It aims to facilitate consensus-building and interoperability of services across disciplines to achieve a shared knowledge representation and knowledge engineering framework.

A comprehensive collection of terminologies can be found in the [Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications \(BARTOC\)](#).

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

Though not a focus of this guideline document, PIDs play an important role in KGs and are worth to be mentioned. While KGs come along with their own PID for every resource, e.g. URIs within RDF graphs, using PIDs like DOIs, URNs, Handles, etc. within the metadata is always useful to increase findability and interoperability.

Depending on which metadata schema has been chosen to represent the data in a KG, a different range of properties can be used to include PIDs. Important in this regard is to follow the official specifications of the PIDs, e.g. the DOI URI scheme specification at <https://doi.org/10.1000/292>, to ensure a correct inclusion of the identifiers and interoperability.

More information about PIDs within NFDI and particularly which PID to choose for which scientific artifact can be found in the PID4NFDI base service at <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>.

Metadata schemas provided by data repositories and aggregators

While the registration of a KG in the [KGI registry](#) relies on metadata using particularly the NFDIcore ontology, other data repositories and aggregators exist which provide their own metadata schemas like [OpenAIRE](#), [DataCite](#), and [re3data](#). Such repositories provide additional features for data providers that go beyond the scope of the KGI registry.

Registering data in such repositories enhances the visibility, accessibility, and impact of research outputs. These platforms provide standardized metadata, persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs), and interoperability frameworks that facilitate data discovery, citation, and reuse across disciplines. By depositing data in such repositories, researchers ensure long-term preservation, compliance with open science principles, and alignment with funder and publisher requirements. Additionally, aggregators improve data linkage and integration, fostering collaboration and enabling broader scientific and societal benefits from shared research data.

Further sources regarding best practices

The topic of Linked Data principles and practices is relatively well documented. We invite the interested reader to explore such practices in a greater depth via the works of Schmachtenberg et al. (2014) on best practices for linking, (re)using vocabularies, and metadata (provenance, licensing, and other information), among other practices; Heath & Bizer (2011) and Dodds & Davis (2012), being just two of the many sources on the topic, provide guidance on best practices for publishing Linked Data.

Example SPARQL Queries

In the following section, we present several examples of SPARQL queries that cover different scopes, including:

- queries that can be executed directly in the KG registry
- queries on single KGs which may also be suitable for the KG registry
- queries on single KGs focusing on specific content that may work on rather selected KGs
- federated queries across at least two KGs

For all the queries we provide links to selected SPARQL endpoints where the queries can be tested. In order to put the example queries into context, we provide two user stories (see below).

About SPARQL queries

The [KGI4NFDI Registry](#) itself is a KG. Due to the technology choice regarding its implementation, we decided to include a brief description of SPARQL to support the KGI Registry access. However, as seen in Table 2, this does not mean that this is the mandatory query language for KGs, and organizations or NFDI consortia creating KGs can make different technology choices from ours. Finally, in addition to the API-based means of KG access, it is not far-fetched to imagine access via more natural language-like interfaces (LLM-based, for example).

A SPARQL query consists of key components, including PREFIX, SELECT (or other query forms like ASK, CONSTRUCT, and DESCRIBE), WHERE, and FILTER clauses. Prefixes define shorthand for long URIs, improving readability and efficiency (e.g., PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>). The WHERE clause contains triple patterns that specify relationships between subjects, predicates, and objects. Naming conventions in SPARQL typically follow RDF and ontology standards, using meaningful URIs, standardized way for variable names (we use lower case and underscores in this guideline), and separating namespaces with colons (e.g., foaf:name). Proper structuring and adherence to these conventions ensure clarity, maintainability, and interoperability of SPARQL queries. For detailed information on SPARQL queries, please refer to (W3C, n.d.).

Naming conventions in SPARQL

For reasons of consistency, we applied the following naming conventions to the SPARQL queries

- SPARQL clauses are written in upper case
- Variables are written in lower case and may contain an underscore to separate words
- Variables are either named in a self-explanatory way or according to their position in a triple (subject, property, object)

Queries

Q1. List the KGs in the KGI registry

This query allows users to get an overview on the KGs included in the KGI registry. The SPARQL endpoint can be found here: <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de/>. Basic metadata (title, publisher, and URL) about each knowledge graph can be retrieved and will be displayed in a table. Optionally, the query can be extended to retrieve further information, e.g. a description and the URL of the Knowledge Graph's SPARQL endpoint. In that case, the SELECT clause has to be extended by `?description` and `?kg_endpoint`.

```
# Query lists all KGs included in the KGI registry.
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT ?title ?publisher ?landing_page_url
WHERE {
  # Retrieves basic dataset metadata
  ?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset .
  ?dataset dcterms:title ?title .
  ?dataset dcterms:publisher ?publisher .
  ?dataset dcat:landingPage ?landing_page_url .
  # Optional: retrieves description
  OPTIONAL { ?dataset dcterms:description ?description .}
  # Optional: retrieves URL of SPARQL endpoint
  OPTIONAL {?dataset dcat:endpointURL ?kg_endpoint .}
}
```

The result of this query is retrieved in a table format where each column represents a variable stated in the SELECT clause, e.g. `?title`, `?publisher`, `?landing_page_URL`. Each row of the table represents a contained Knowledge Graph of the KGI registry.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- KGI registry: <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de/>

Q2. Count the total number of triples in the KGI registry (or in any other KG)

This query allows users to assess the size of a particular KG. The total number of triples (`?number_of_triples`) in a KG is returned and displayed via this query. The higher number indicates that KG is large and has a potentially complex graph. The more substantial number suggests that the KG requires more resources and a longer time to query; therefore, a more optimized query is needed for such knowledge graphs. In the given query, `COUNT` is an aggregate function that counts the number of `?subject ?predicate ?object` cases in a KG.

```
# Query retrieves the total number of triples in a KG
SELECT (COUNT(*) AS ?number_of_triples)
WHERE {
    ?subject ?predicate ?object .
}
```

The query's result is an integer value returned in a table format.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- KGI registry: <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q3. Get a sample of triples in the KG

This SPARQL query retrieves a sample of triples from a KG. The query matches any triple in the KG since there are no filters or constraints, essentially giving a sample of 100 data entries from the graph.

```
# Get a sample of triples in the KG
SELECT *
WHERE {
    ?subject ?predicate ?object.
}
LIMIT 100
```

The query's result is a table where each column represents a component of a triple (subject, predicate, object).

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- KGI registry: <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakt: <https://query.semantic-kompakt.de/>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q4. Explore the data and the data model for a sample resource in a KG

A known resource from a KG or a resource chosen from the results of query Q3 can be further investigated in terms of the associated data contained in the KG and how it is represented in the data model of the KG. This query describes the resource denoted below via <URI>.

```
# Get a description of a given resource.
```

```
DESCRIBE <URI>
```

Example from MaRDI:

```
DESCRIBE <https://portal.mardi4nfdi.de/entity/Q641846>
```

The query's result is a table where each column represents a component of a triple (subject, predicate, object). In the rows of that table, all triples are listed that hold information about the <URI>. This also allows further insight into the underlying data model by exposing the used predicates and objects.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- KGI registry: <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakt: <https://query.semantic-kompakt.de/>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q5. List all distinct types in a KG (including the KGI Registry)

In a KG, entities are often categorized into one or more classes. The given query lists unique classes of entity types. This helps the user to understand the entity categories in the KG's ontology and write entity-specific queries. In the given query, `?subject` denotes entities while `?type` is the URI of classes that are usually `rdf:type`. `DISTINCT` is an aggregate function that returns unique values of `?type`. Alternatively, one can use `GROUP BY` clause on `?type` and `COUNT` aggregate function, which returns unique `?type` as well as the count of the occurrence of `?type`.

```
# List all distinct entity types in the graph
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?type
WHERE {
    ?subject rdf:type ?type.
}
```

The result of this query is returned as a single column, where each cell is a URL of entity type.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- KGI registry: <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q6. List all distinct properties in a KG

This query retrieves a unique list of all properties present in the knowledge graph. It helps the user understand the range of relationships or attributes defined in the knowledge graph. Alternatively, one can use the GROUP BY clause on ?property and use the COUNT aggregate function to get the total instances of each property present in a KG.

```
# List all distinct properties in the graph
SELECT DISTINCT ?property
WHERE {
    ?subject ?property ?object.
}
```

This query returns a single column containing a list of properties in URL format.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q7. Count the occurrences of distinct types

This query is similar to query #3. The given query lists unique classes of entity types. In addition to distinct types, this query also shows the total number of type instances present in the KG. Here, the `GROUP BY` clause need to be added if the KG provides a query portal (instead of sparql endpoint), as the parser requires the `COUNT` function to be accompanied by the `GROUP BY` clause. In the SPARQL endpoint of Virtuoso, users do not need to provide the `GROUP BY` clause as it is implied while counting the number of instances. Similarly, the `ORDER BY` clause sorts the result such that the highest occurring types are listed at the top. This helps users understand the prominent classes/types used in a KG.

```
# Counting the occurrences of distinct types in the graph
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?type (COUNT(*) as ?occurrence)
WHERE {
    ?subject rdf:type ?type.
}
```

or

```
# Counting the occurrence of distinct types in the graph
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?type (COUNT(*) as ?occurrence)
WHERE {
    ?subject rdf:type ?type
}
GROUP BY ?type
ORDER BY DESC(?occurrence)
```

This result is formatted as a table where there are two columns, namely `?type` and `?occurrence`. They denote the URL of the entity type and the number of triple instances in which they occur. While the results of the first query are unsorted, the table is sorted for the second query, so that the highest occurring types are at the top.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q8. Count the occurrence of distinct properties

This query is similar to query Q6. The given query lists unique properties in a KG. In addition to distinct properties, this query also shows the total number of properties instances present in the KG. As in query #5, the user must add a GroupBy clause if the KG provides a query portal, as the parser requires the COUNT function to be accompanied by the GroupBy clause. In the SPARQL endpoint of Virtuoso, users do not need to provide GROUP BY clause as it is implied while counting the number of instances. Similarly, the ORDER BY clause sorts the result such that the highest occurring properties are listed at the top. This helps users understand the prominent properties used in a KG.

```
# Counting the occurrence of distinct properties in the graph
SELECT DISTINCT ?property (COUNT(*) as ?occurrence)
WHERE {
    ?subject ?property ?object
}
GROUP BY ?property
ORDER BY DESC(?occurrence)
```

This result is formatted as a table where there are two columns, namely ?type and ?occurrence. They denote the URL of the properties entities are linked with, and the number of triple instances in which they occur. The table is sorted so that the highest occurring properties are at the top.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q9. List the base IRI of the URIs of each entities used in a KGs

This query extracts and returns a unique list of base IRIs, which are derived from the predicate IRIs of all triples by removing their final segments using a regex and binding the base IRI to a variable. This helps to display the namespaces or hosting websites for properties in the dataset.

- **?type:** Represents the predicate IRI of each triple.
- **BIND Clause:** Uses `REPLACE(str(?type), "(.*)[/|#][^/#]*$", "$1")` to remove the final segment from the string representation of ?type, capturing the base URL or namespace. It binds the resulting string to ?hosting_website.
- **IRI Conversion:** The `IRI(?hosting_website)` function converts the extracted string back into an IRI format and assigns it to ?base_IRI in the `SELECT` clause.
- **SELECT DISTINCT** ensures that the final result only contains unique base IRIs.
- **LIMIT** is used to specify the maximum number of results. This command can be very helpful when exploring KGs and to reduce computation power.

```
# Extracts and returns a unique list of base IRIs
SELECT DISTINCT (IRI(?hosting_website) AS ?base_IRI)
WHERE {
    ?subject ?type ?object.
    BIND(REPLACE(str(?type), "(.*)[/|#][^/#]*$", "$1") AS ?hosting_website)
}
LIMIT 10
```

The query returns a single-column table where each row shows a distinct ?base_IRI (an IRI value) representing the hosting website or namespace from which a predicate originates.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- SemanticKompakt: <https://query.semantic-kompakt.de/>
- Linked Stage Graph: <https://slod.fiz-karlsruhe.de/sparql>

Q10. List the (subject, predicate, object) names (exclude base URI) if the object has no `rdfs:type`

This query extracts distinct local names for a subject's class, predicate, and object's class from triples by stripping off their namespace. It provides insights into the relationships between different classes in the graph by showing how entities of specific courses (subjects and objects) are connected via particular properties, all expressed in a simplified, namespace-free format.

This query can be computationally intensive and could result in a timeout. For this reason, a `LIMIT` clause has been added.

```
# List subject, object and predicate without the base URI.
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?subject_name ?property_name ?object_name
WHERE {
  {
    ?subject ?type_URI_predicate ?object.
    ?subject rdf:type ?type_URI_subject.
    ?object rdf:type ?type_URI_object.
  }
  BIND(REPLACE(str(?type_URI_subject), "(.*)/(|\\#)([^/\\#]*$)", "$3") AS
?subject_name)
  BIND(REPLACE(str(?type_URI_object), "(.*)/(|\\#)([^/\\#]*$)", "$3") AS
?object_name)
  BIND(REPLACE(str(?type_URI_predicate), "(.*)/(|\\#)([^/\\#]*$)", "$3") AS
?property_name)
}
LIMIT 10
```

This query returns a unique table with three columns: one for the subject's local name, one for the property local name, and one for the object's local name.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- SemanticKompakt: <https://query.semantic-kompakt.de/>
- SoftwareKG: <https://data.gesis.org/softwarekg/sparql>

Q11. Distinct properties and types with examples

This query retrieves distinct URIs used either as an RDF type (in type assertions) or as a property in triples. It is also a sample instance for each type when available. This structure helps to understand how various URIs are used within the graph, either as classes (types) or properties, and gives you an example instance for each type when possible.

This query can be computationally intensive and could result in a timeout. For this reason, a `LIMIT` clause has been added.

```
# List properties and types with example instances from the graph
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?type (SAMPLE(?example_) AS ?example)
WHERE {
  {
    ?example_ rdf:type ?type.
  } UNION {
    ?subject ?type ?object.
  }
}
GROUP BY ?type
LIMIT 5
```

The query outputs a table with two columns:

- `?type`: A distinct URI used as either an RDF type or a property.
- `?example`: A sample instance (if available) that demonstrates the usage of the `?type` from the first branch.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>

Q12. Entities with the highest number of occurrence

This query identifies the top ten non-literal entities that appear most frequently across all triples - whether as subject, predicate, or object. It helps reveal which entities are most central to a KG or often referenced in a KG, providing insights into the data's structure and key nodes.

This query can be computationally intensive and could result in a timeout. For this reason, a `LIMIT` clause has been added.

```
# Retrieving the non-literal entities with the highest number of occurrence
SELECT ?entity (COUNT(*) AS ?number_of_occurrence)
WHERE {
  {
    { ?entity ?predicate ?object }
    UNION
    { ?subject ?predicate ?entity }
    UNION
    { ?subject ?entity ?object }
  }
  FILTER(!isLiteral(?entity))
}
GROUP BY ?entity
ORDER BY DESC(?number_of_occurrence)
LIMIT 10
```

The output is a table with two columns:

- `?entity`: The non-literal entity from the dataset.
- `?number_of_occurrence`: The count of triples in which that entity appears.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>

Q13. Entities with the lowest number of occurrence

This query identifies the 10 non-literal entities that appear the least frequently across all triples - whether as subject, predicate, or object - by counting and grouping their occurrences in ascending order. It helps reveal which entities are least referenced in a KG, providing insights into entities that are not widely used in a KG. This helps in identifying outliers or gaps, if they exist in a KG. In some cases, it helps in detecting inconsistencies or errors. The given queries exclude the literal values using the `FILTER` clause with `isLiteral` function. `isLiteral` takes an instance of node and returns `True` if the value is a literal, i.e., text, datetime, etc.

This query can be computationally intensive and could result in a timeout. For this reason, a `LIMIT` clause has been added.

```
# Retrieving the non-literal entities with the lowest number of occurrence
SELECT ?entity (COUNT(*) AS ?number_of_occurrence)
WHERE {
  {
    { ?entity ?predicate ?object }
    UNION
    { ?subject ?predicate ?entity }
    UNION
    { ?subject ?entity ?object }
  }
  FILTER(!isLiteral(?entity))
}
GROUP BY ?entity
ORDER BY ASC(?number_of_occurrence)
LIMIT 10
```

The output is a table with two columns:

- `?entity`: The non-literal entity from the dataset.
- `?number_of_occurrence`: The count of triples in which that entity appears.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakkt: <https://query.semantic-kompakkt.de/>

Q14. Languages used in the strings of a KG

This query extracts distinct language tags from literal values in the graph and counts the language covered by a KG and proportion of dataset represented in each language, grouping the results by language tag.

It provides insight into the linguistic distribution of data in a knowledge graph, enabling to assess language coverage and tailor multilingual support or analysis. The `LANG` function takes the `?literal` and returns the language tag which is usually represented by appending language tags for example: `en`, `fr`, etc. after a literal using `@tag`.

```
# Lists the languages covered by KG and the total number of literal instances
for each language.

SELECT DISTINCT ?language (COUNT(*) AS ?number)
WHERE {
    ?subject ?predicate ?literal .
    BIND(LANG(?literal) AS ?language)
    FILTER(isLiteral(?literal))
    FILTER(LANG(?literal) != "") # Only include literals with a non-empty language
tag
}
GROUP BY ?language # Group by the alias ?language assigned in the SELECT clause
```

The query returns a table with two columns:

- `?language`: The distinct language tag (e.g., "en", "fr").
- `?number`: The count of literal values that have that particular language tag.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakt: <https://query.semantic-kompakt.de/>

Q15. Querying for owl:sameAs or schema:sameAs links to see connections to other KGs

This query retrieves all owl:sameAs or schema:sameAs links, linking entities to their equivalents in external knowledge graphs. It enables users to identify cross-references between different datasets, facilitating data integration, validation, and enhanced semantic understanding across knowledge graphs. The UNION clause combines triples containing sameAs property from owl and schema. The BIND clause assigns the property sameAs from owl and schema, if they exist in KG, to variable ?predicate.

```
# Lists all triples containing owl:SameAs or schema:sameAs property.
PREFIX owl: http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#
PREFIX schema: http://schema.org/
SELECT ?subject ?predicate ?object
WHERE {
  {
    ?subject owl:sameAs ?object .
    BIND(owl:sameAs AS ?predicate)
  }
}
```

This query returns a table with ?subject ?predicate ?object columns , where each row contains a triple instance where the predicate is sameAs, and the subject and object refer to the same entity.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>
- SoftwareKG: <https://data.gesis.org/softwarekg/sparql>
- Linked Stage Graph: <https://slod.fiz-karlsruhe.de/sparql>

Q16. PIDs present in a KG

The following four queries retrieve triples containing specific PIDs. While the examples investigate the occurrences of DOIs, ORCID, Handles, and ISBN numbers, they can easily be adapted towards other PIDs.

Q16a. DOI

This query filters literal values to extract DOIs and returns distinct DOI instances and their corresponding types, properties, and objects.

It enables users to identify and consolidate unique DOI references in the knowledge graph, facilitating enhanced tracking of publication links, improved metadata consistency, and better interconnection with external scholarly resources. In the given query, the `FILTER` function takes two conditions. First, it checks if the object is a literal (`isLiteral`), and next, `REGEX` tries to match the object that matches the pattern of DOI.

```
# Check if a KG contains DOIs and lists the unique DOIs along with their types,
property and object.
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?type ?predicate ?pid_type ?object
WHERE {
  ?subject rdf:type ?type .
  ?subject ?predicate ?object .
  FILTER (isLiteral(?object))
  BIND(IF(REGEX(?object, "^(DOI:\\s*)?10\\.\\.\\d{4,9}/[-._;()/:A-Z0-9]+$", "i"),
"DOI", "Other") AS ?pid_type)
  FILTER (?pid_type = "DOI") # Ensures only objects with identified PID types
are returned
}
LIMIT 10
```

Result returns the formatted table where each row represents a triple instance and `?object` represents literals that matches the pattern `^(DOI:\\s*)?10\\.\\.\\d{4,9}/[-._;()/:A-Z0-9]+$` i.e. an DOI identifier. `LIMIT 100` restricts the number of results returned to 100, which is useful for managing large result sets, pagination, and improving query performance.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- MaRDI: <https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/>

Q16b. ORCID

This query filters literal values to extract ORCID identifiers and returns distinct ORCID instances and their corresponding types, properties, and objects.

It enables identifying and consolidating unique researcher profiles in the knowledge graph, enhancing data integration, validation, and cross-referencing of scholarly contributions across multiple datasets. In the given query, the FILTER function takes two conditions. First, it checks if the object is a literal (`isLiteral`), and next, REGEX tries to match the object that follows the pattern of ORCID.

```
# Check if a KG contains ORCID identifiers and lists the unique ORCID along with
their types, property and object.
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?type ?predicate ?object ?pid_type
WHERE {
    ?subject rdf:type ?type .
    ?subject ?predicate ?object .
    FILTER (isLiteral(?object))
    BIND(IF(REGEX(?object, "^https://orcid\\.org/\\d{4}-\\d{4}-\\d{4}-\\d{4}$",
    "i"), "ORCID", "Other" ) AS ?pid_type)
    FILTER (?pid_type = "ORCID") # Ensures only objects with identified PID types
are returned
}
LIMIT 10
```

The result returns the formatted table where each row represents a triple instance and `?object` represents literals that matches the pattern `"^https://orcid\\.org/\\d{4}-\\d{4}-\\d{4}-\\d{4}$"` i.e. an ORCID identifier. `LIMIT 100` restricts the number of results returned to 100, which is useful for managing large result sets, pagination, and improving query performance.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- ORKG: <https://orkg.org/triplestore>

Q16c. Handle

This query filters literal values to extract Handles and returns distinct Handle instances and their corresponding types, properties, and objects.

It enables the identification of unique handles in the knowledge graph, promoting improved metadata consistency, cross-referencing, and integration with external datasets. In the given query, the `FILTER` function takes two conditions. First, it checks if the object is a literal (`isLiteral`), and next, `REGEX` tries to match the object that follows the pattern of Handle.

```
# Check if a KG contains Handles and lists the unique Handles along with their
types, property and object.
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?subject ?predicate ?object
WHERE {
  {
    ?subject ?predicate ?object .
    FILTER (
      isLiteral(?object) &&
      REGEX(str(?object), "^hdl:[0-9]+/[0-9A-Za-z]+")
    )
  }
  UNION
  {
    ?subject ?predicate ?object .
    FILTER (
      isURI(?object) &&
      REGEX(str(?object), "^http://hdl.handle.net/[0-9]+/[0-9A-Za-z]+")
    )
  }
}
LIMIT 10
```

The result returns the formatted table where each row represents a triple instance and `?object` represents literals that match the pattern `"^hdl:[0-9]+/[0-9A-Za-z]+"` i.e. an ISBN identifier. `LIMIT 100` restricts the number of results returned to 100, which is useful for managing large result sets, pagination, and improving query performance.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>

Q16d. ISBN

This query filters literal values to extract ISBNs and returns distinct ISBN instances and their corresponding types, properties, and objects.

It identifies unique ISBN references in the knowledge graph, enhances bibliographic integration, ensures metadata consistency, and facilitates cross-referencing with external library and publication data sources. In the given query, FILTER function takes two conditions, First it checks if the object is a literal (isLiteral) and next, REGEX tries to match the object that follows the pattern of ISBN.

```
# Check if a KG contains ISBN identifiers and list the unique ISBNs types,
predicates and objects.
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
SELECT DISTINCT ?subject ?predicate ?object
WHERE {
  ?subject ?predicate ?object .
  FILTER (
    isLiteral(?object) &&
    REGEX(str(?object), "^(?=(?:\\D*\\d){10}(?:(?:\\D*\\d){3})?)[\\d-]+$")
  )
}
LIMIT 10
```

Result returns the formatted table where each row represents a triple instance and ?object represents literals that matches the pattern "^(?=(?:\\D*\\d){10}(?:(?:\\D*\\d){3})?)[\\d-]+\$" i.e. an ISBN identifier. LIMIT 100 restricts the number of results returned to 100, which is useful for managing large result sets, pagination, and improving query performance.

Sample SPARQL endpoints where you can test this query:

- GESIS KG: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/sparql>
- SemanticKompakt: <https://query.semantic-kompakt.de/>

Query exploration stories

Queries are often not done in “isolation”, and users often start with exploratory queries to understand the structure and the content of a KG, before finalizing their queries. We can think of these queries as being part of a query “story” that the user follows to the desired result from the interaction with the KG. In this part, we consider a few personas in the role for such query stories.

Story 1

Aleena is a researcher who has interdisciplinary research interests, with a focus on the domain of bioinformatics. Her routine tasks include searching for items of this domain in other related (KG-based) collections and assessing such content. She decides to refer to the KGI Registry service to support her research data quest.

Query 1.1 provides the list of potential KGs to explore: the title, publisher, and landing pages of the KGs could provide an initial indicator for this. Since the list is not that long, it is possible to scroll through the results and identify KGs of interest. From the list, Wikidata seems to be generic enough to contain information on the domain the researcher is primarily interested in: based on the bioinformatics type (Q128570), she wants to see how many related entities are represented in this KG (Listing 1.1).

```
# The number of entities represented of type “bioinformatics” in Wikidata
SELECT (COUNT(?res) AS ?total_instances)
WHERE {
    ?res wdt:P31 wd:Q128570 .
}
```

Listing 1.1. A [query](#) to count the number of entities typed with “bioinformatics”

To get additional information on these instances, she conducts the following query:

```
# List the properties associated with the entity type “bioinformatics”
SELECT DISTINCT ?properties
WHERE {
    ?res wdt:P31 wd:Q128570 ;
        ?properties ?objects .
}
```

Listing 1.2. [Explore](#) the attributes of the entities of type “bioinformatics”

The results about the three entities of this type in Wikidata have a few properties to explore, such as their publication date, website, to name a few.

Query 1.2: In order to explore with a slightly border scope, she settles for the topic of *biology*. Similarly to the previous case, she explores the entities “typed” with biology (Listing 1.3), for which she gets 42 results; when filtering for labels in English, she is left with 14 results to choose from.

```

# List the entities typed with "biology", including their labels
SELECT (COUNT(?item) As ?items)
WHERE {
    ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q420 ;
        rdfs:label ?itemLabel .
}

```

Listing 1.3. [List](#) the number of entities typed with "biology" to get a sense of coverage of such resources in the KG collection.

To have additional information around the entities, she explores the relationships in which the entities from the previous listing appear in (Listing 1.4). This time, there are 68 results, with more properties for Aleena to consider. Considering that KGs are continuously being updated, running this query "story" could result with slightly different - and even more - results.

```

# List the properties associated with the entities of this type
SELECT DISTINCT ?p
WHERE {
    ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q420 ;
        ?p ?o.
}

```

Listing 1.4. [Explore](#) the attributes of the entities of type "biology", which could provide new ideas for querying the graph around this entity.

Query 1.3: Finally, she wants to explore the datasets on the subject of biology available in Wikidata. The query (Listing 1.5) specifies entities of type "dataset" (wd:Q1172284), with a subject (p:P921) of biology (wd:Q420). Initially, she decides to limit the results set (a good measure to have a timely response from a public KG) to 100 results.

```

# Dataset entities and their labels
SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel
WHERE {
    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language
"[AUTO_LANGUAGE],mul,en". }
    {
        SELECT DISTINCT ?item WHERE {
            ?item p:P31 ?statement0.

```

```

    ?statement0 (ps:P31/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q1172284.
    ?item p:P921 ?statement1.
    ?statement1 (ps:P921/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q420.
  }
LIMIT 100
}
}

```

Listing 1.5. [List](#) the datasets with “biology” as their subject matter, limited to 100 results. Additionally, also include the corresponding labels for a reference.

Query 1.4: One path she decides to choose is to check the papers that datasets are used to support or mentioned in. The [Data set KG](#) provides data set mentions in research publications, and it provides several options to complement her results from Query 1.3, such as the most influential authors in the field of biology, datasets from a certain author (based on their ORCID), or papers linked to datasets (ranked) (see the examples [here](#)). Currently, the SPARQL endpoint for this KG is in maintenance mode, thus we could not provide any concrete results, but we will update this query once the SPARQL endpoint is available again. Based on the scenario, however, this remains an interesting query path to pursue to get more information (in Wikidata) about the datasets cited in the literature (Data set KG).

Story 2

Jane is interested in the history of mathematics. She knows that MaRDI runs a mathematical knowledge graph and that NFDI4Memory runs a historical one. She considers how the two graphs might overlap. One dimension of potential overlap is time. Others could be people, locations or architecture. So, she decides to start by watching out for queries or documentation mentioning such dimensions..

At the FactGrid's main page https://database.factgrid.de/wiki/Main_Page , there is a sidebar link labeled "[Sample queries](#)", which leads to the page https://database.factgrid.de/wiki/FactGrid:Sample_queries that has a section "[Looking for dates](#)" which comes with the example query "[All the members of the "Fruchtbringende Gesellschaft" with dates of birth and statement of exactness](#)" that gives a list of entities about humans, including (optionally) their birth dates. Inspecting the items for some of these people manually, Jane notices that some of them have a "[career statement](#)" but she cannot find one that has anything to do with mathematics. So she [searches for "mathematics"](#) in the FactGrid wiki, which yields some hits. She thus writes a query aimed at finding career statements related to mathematics.

Query 2.1

```
# Career statements whose English label includes the string "math"
SELECT DISTINCT ?career ?careerstring
WHERE {
  ?FactGrid_mathematician wdt:P165 ?career.
  ?career rdfs:label ?careerstring .
  FILTER (LANG(?careerstring) = "en" )
  FILTER (REGEX(LCASE(STR(?careerstring)), "math"))
  FILTER (?career != wd:Q448328 )
}
```

Listing 1.6. [FactGrid query example](#): It looks for items (likely people) that have a "career statement" (FactGrid P165), then gets their English labels, lowercase-normalizes them and checks for the presence of the string "math". The last line removes results for "polymath" (FactGrid Q448328), which is not specific enough for a mathematics-focused query. The query gave 13 results.

Query 2.2

Building on these initial results, Jane now asks FactGrid for a map of people with such career statements in Paris.

```
# Map of street addresses of mathematicians in Paris
#defaultView:Map
SELECT DISTINCT ?FactGrid_mathematician ?FactGrid_mathematicianLabel
?FactGrid_addressLabel ?FactGrid_coord
WHERE {
  ?FactGrid_mathematician wdt:P165 ?career.
```

```

?career rdfs:label ?careerstring.
FILTER((LANG(?careerstring)) = "en")
FILTER(REGEX(LCASE(?careerstring), "math"))
FILTER(?career != wd:Q448328)

?FactGrid_mathematician wdt:P38 ?date_of_death;
                        wdt:P208 ?FactGrid_address.

?FactGrid_address wdt:P48 ?FactGrid_coord;
                  wdt:P47 wd:Q10441.

SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language
"[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
}

```

Listing 1.7. [FactGrid query example](#): It looks for items that have a career statement as per Query 2.1 (whose components are highlighted in grey), then asks for street addresses (only for deceased people) and filters these for Paris and plots them on a map. This gave 34 results.

Query 2.3

Having explored FactGrid this far, Jane is now turning to MaRDI to see whether she can get similar kinds of results from there. She starts by [searching MaRDI for “FactGrid”](#), which quickly leads to the MaRDI property [FactGrid item ID \(P316\)](#) that might be useful to combine the two knowledge graphs.

```

# People in MaRDI with known FactGrid ID
SELECT DISTINCT ?MaRDI_person ?MaRDI_personLabel
WHERE {
  ?MaRDI_person wdt:P31 wd:Q57162;
                wdt:P316 ?FactGrid_personID.

  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language
"[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
}

```

Listing 1.8. [MaRDI query example](#): This query checks MaRDI for instances (MaRDI P31) of humans (MaRDI Q57162) with a FactGrid item ID (MaRDI P316) statement. The number of results was 1868 .

Query 2.4

The queries 2.2 and 2.3 can then be combined in what is called a federated query from MaRDI to FactGrid. In order to do that, variable names and types, along with their URL patterns as well as the URL of the secondary query service (in this case FactGrid), need to be specified correctly. For more detailed information on this, see the [Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\)](#).

```

# title: Street addresses of historic mathematicians in Paris
# This query combines data from
# https://query.portal.mardi4nfdi.de (MaRDI)
# and https://database.factgrid.de/ (NFDI4Memory)
#defaultView:Map{"hide":["?FactGrid_coord"]}
PREFIX FactGrid_wd: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
PREFIX FactGrid_wdt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>

SELECT DISTINCT
  ?FactGrid_mathematician ?FactGrid_mathematicianLabel ?FactGrid_addressLabel
  ?FactGrid_coord
  ?MaRDI_person ?MaRDI_personLabel WHERE {
  ?MaRDI_person wdt:P316 ?FactGrid_personID .

  BIND(URI(CONCAT("https://database.factgrid.de/entity/", ?FactGrid_personID))
  AS ?FactGrid_mathematician)

  SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
    SELECT DISTINCT
      ?FactGrid_mathematician ?FactGrid_mathematicianLabel ?FactGrid_addressLabel
      ?FactGrid_coord
      WHERE
        {
          ?FactGrid_mathematician FactGrid_wdt:P165 ?career.
          ?career rdfs:label ?careerstring .
          FILTER (LANG(?careerstring) = "en" )
          FILTER (REGEX(LCASE(?careerstring), "math"))
          FILTER(?career != FactGrid_wd:Q448328)
          ?FactGrid_mathematician FactGrid_wdt:P38 ?date_of_death;
            FactGrid_wdt:P208 ?FactGrid_address.
          ?FactGrid_address FactGrid_wdt:P48 ?FactGrid_coord;
            FactGrid_wdt:P47 FactGrid_wd:Q10441 .

          SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language
            "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
        }

    LIMIT 100
  }
}

```

```
    BIND(?FactGrid_mathematicianLabel AS ?mathematicianLabel)
    BIND(STR(CONCAT("MaRDI: ", STR(?mathematicianLabel))) AS ?MaRDI_personLabel)
}
```

Listing 1.9. [Federated MaRDI-FactGrid query example](#): Map of street addresses of mathematicians in Paris - similar to but different from query 2.2, whose key parts are included here in blue, while the core of query 2.3 is included in light magenta. Further adjustments of query 2.2 for federation are highlighted in light yellow. This query yields 15 results, i.e. less than half of what was returned by query 2.2. If the remnants of query 1.1 (in light grey) are commented out or removed, this number rises to 32, which is similar to the 34 of query 2.2 and thus a good starting point for diving deeper into the data and associated workflows.

References

- Dodds, L., & Davis, I. (2012). Linked data patterns. <http://patterns.dataincubator.org/book> [Accessed March 20, 2025]
- Heath, T., & Bizer, C. (2011). Linked data: Evolving the web into a global data space (1st ed.). Synthesis Lectures on the Semantic Web: Theory and Technology, 1(1), 1–136. Morgan & Claypool. <http://linkeddatabook.com/book>
- Limani, F. (2025). KGI4NFDI - Requirements analysis report 2024 (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717742>
- Schmachtenberg, M., Bizer, C., & Paulheim, H. (2014). Adoption of the Linked Data best practices in different topical domains. In P. Mika et al. (Eds.), The Semantic Web – ISWC 2014 (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 8796). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11964-9_16
- W3C. (n.d.). SPARQL 1.1 query language. <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/> [Accessed March 20, 2025]